

Sucrase Assay Kit Instruction

1. Principle of Measurement

Sucrase catalyzes the hydrolysis of sucrose or others with the similar structure. The product would be further oxidized in the presence of certain types of enzymes (e.g., Glucose Oxidase) to form Hydrogen Peroxide (H_2O_2). Chromogenic agent in the solution combines with the H_2O_2 generated to give the red product. The spectrum absorbance at certain wavelength which is proportion to the concentration of the red product can be analyzed by means of spectrophotometer in order to determine the activity of sucrase in the sample.

2. Reagent Composition & Preparation

Reagent I: 2 Bottles of powder. 2 bottle of diluent (5mL each) which is colorless and transparent. Both should be preserved at 2-8°C and is stable for half a year.

Substrate Preparation: 5mL diluent is mixed with one bottle of powder till fully dissolved. Preserved at 2-8°C for 48 hours.

Reagent II: 1 Bottle of terminator (5mL). Preserved at room temperature. Note that when the temperature is low, the reagent may be frozen. Under this circumstance, the reagent should be warmed in water bath to obtain transparent solution before use.

Reagent III: 1 Bottle of liquid with 25mL preserved at 2-8°C for 6 months.

Reagent IV: 1 Bottle of liquid with 25mL preserve at 2-8°C for 6 months.

Chromogenic Agent Preparation: Equally and fully mix reagent III and IV and the mixture can be preserved at 2-8°C for 30 days.

Glucose standard solution with the concentration of 5.55mmol/L and this can be preserved at 2-8°C for half a year.

3. Procedures of Measurement

Solution Composition (μL)	Blank	Standard	Sample	Comparison
Double Distilled Water	10			
5.55mmol/L Glucose Solution		10		
Sample			10	
Substrate	20	20	20	20
Terminator	10	10	10	10
Chromogenic Agent	1000	1000	1000	1000
Sample				10

Every solution is mixed and heated in water bath with 37°C for 15 minutes.

The equipment is adjusted to zero with double distilled water, and then the optical density (OD) of each tube is measured at the wavelength of 505nm using cuvettes with 0.5cm path length.

Note 1. The method gives stable results. However, this method requires to measure the four tubes simultaneously. The blank tube should be compared with the standard one while the sample tube is compared to the remaining one.

Note 2. Before analyzing massive number of samples, a series of experiments should be operated in order to obtain the best concentration values. Normally, the OD value should be below 0.5 to give the best result.

4. Unit Definition & Calculation Formula

Under the condition of 37°C and pH=6.0, one sucrase activity unit is defined as one mmol sucrose hydrolyzed by 1mg protein per minute.

Calculation Formula

$$\text{Sucrase Activity } \frac{U}{\text{mgprot}} = \frac{OD_{\text{Sample}} - OD_{\text{Comparison}}}{OD_{\text{Standard}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}} \times \frac{C_{\text{Standard}}}{(5.55\text{mmol/L})} \div \frac{t}{20 \text{ min}} \div \frac{C_{\text{Pro}}}{(\text{mgprot/ml})} \times 1000$$

5. Calculation Example

Freshly prepared 10% homogenate of mucous membrane from mouse intestinal was used as the sample. The sample was handled and the OD results are 0.000, 0.138, 0.148 and 0.011 in accordance to the sequence in the list. The protein concentration in this homogenate is 1.542mg/mL.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Sucrase Activity } \frac{U}{\text{mgprot}} &= \frac{OD_{\text{Sample}} - OD_{\text{Comparison}}}{OD_{\text{Standard}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}} \times \frac{C_{\text{Standard}}}{(5.55\text{mmol/L})} \div \frac{t}{20 \text{ min}} \div \frac{C_{\text{Pro}}}{(\text{mgprot/ml})} \times 1000 \\ &= \frac{0.148 - 0.011}{0.138 - 0.000} \times 5.55 \div 20 \div 1.542 \times 1000 (U/\text{mgprot}) = 1.787 \times 10^2 (U/\text{mgprot}) \end{aligned}$$